

Recurrent Giant Pilomatricoma of the Lower Back in a Young Adult: A Rare Case Report

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Introduction

A pilomatricoma, also known as calcifying epithelioma of Malherbe, is a rare benign adnexal tumor arising from hair matrix cells. It typically presents as a small, firm, slow-growing nodule in children and young adults, most commonly in the head and neck region. Large lesions (>5cm) and recurrent forms are uncommon, especially in atypical anatomical locations. Malignant transformation is exceptional. Recurrent lesions raise clinical concern which should lead to prompt treatment.

Case Presentation

In this case, a 27 year old healthy male presented with a large, painless mass in the right lower back. He had no other co-morbidities. Initially the lesion was thought to be an epidermoid cyst, hence a partial excision was performed under local anaesthesia. The histopathology report confirmed a pilomatricoma. One year later, the patient returned with a recurrent lump. Its size had increased. An ultrasound confirmed a lesion measuring 7.5 x 7.0 cm x 5.0 cm. Complete surgical excision under general anaesthesia was subsequently planned and performed. Histopathological report once again confirmed a benign pilomatricoma. The patient recovered and was discharged with no further complaints.

Conclusion

This case illustrates an unusual presentation of pilomatricoma. This is due to its large size, recurrence, and atypical location in the lower back. Clinicians must recognise that recurrent subcutaneous “cysts” are not always epidermoid lesions and any large or atypically located nodules in young adults warrant consideration of pilomatricoma. Complete surgical excision with histopathological confirmation is essential to prevent misdiagnosis, to avoid repeated inadequate procedures, and to exclude rare malignant transformations. This case underlines the importance of considering pilomatricoma in the differential diagnosis of subcutaneous masses in uncommon locations.

Keywords

Pilomatricoma; Recurrent pilomatricoma; Lower back mass; Surgical excision